

Surgical Management in High Grade Spondylolisthesis**Channabasava¹, Abhilash Kumar. G², Amaresh³**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopedics, Raichur Institute of Medical Sciences, Raichur, Karnataka, India²Junior Resident, Department of Orthopedics, Raichur Institute of Medical Sciences, Raichur, Karnataka, India³Junior Resident, Department of Orthopedics, Raichur Institute of Medical Sciences, Raichur, Karnataka, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Aims and Objective:** To study the functional outcome in high grade spondylolisthesis of lumbar & sacral vertebrae patients post-surgery.**Methodology:** a Retrospective study of 30 all patients who underwent posterior instrumentation of lumbar & sacral spine surgery in Department of orthopaedics in Raichur institute of medical sciences, Raichur, Karnataka from September 2022 to September 2023.**Results:** 30 patients with high-grade spondylolisthesis at L5-S1 were operated using this progressive reduction technique, representing 14 patients grade III (28%), 15 patients grade IV (57%) and one patient grade I (15%). All procedure was performed in a single operation using a posterior approach. All patients were upright on the second postoperative day. The median follow-up was 12 months. Six months after surgery, 6 patients were pain free and able to stay home without disability. Only one patient presented persistent L5 sciatalgia. Even if, there was one patient with persistent pain, all of them maintained or improved their daily activities. All patients had good outcomes and returned to their full normal activities within 6 months after surgery. None patient developed deep or superficial infection.**Conclusion:** The purpose of this study was to describe technique reduction and results for treatment of high-grade spondylolisthesis with a progressive, single-staged, posteriorly and without forced reduction, sometimes combined to trans-vertebral trans-sacral for restoration of lumbosacral alignment and analyses functional and radiological outcomes.**Keywords:** HGS (High – Grade Spondylolisthesis, Posterior Instrumentation, Pedicle Screw Fixation.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

High-grade spondylolisthesis (HGS) is an uncommon cause of lower back pain in adults. Spondylolisthesis refers to the forward translation of one vertebral body relative to another directly below. Most often, spondylolisthesis results secondary to an anatomic defect in the pars interarticularis of the lumbar spine. The specifier “high-grade” implies a slippage of one vertebral body by greater than 50%. HGS is found in approximately 11.3% in those with spondylolisthesis.

Multiple etiologies can lead to HGS. Most often, either congenital anomalies predisposing to spondylosis and slip progression or gradual degeneration of the posterior facet joints (dysplastic), or defects in the pars interarticularis (isthmic) are responsible. However, other types such as traumatic and pathologic also exist. With the

rapid evolution of surgical techniques, in conjunction with developments in nuclear medicine and diagnostic modalities, the evaluation and management of this deformity in adults has become increasingly complex.

The purpose of the current article is to provide a comprehensive review on current concepts in the management and evaluation of the adult patient population with HGS. Together, this review will provide a better background and understanding of HGS in adults and an update on currently accepted concepts in evaluation and management.

Basic Terminology and Classifications

The term spondylolisthesis refers to the forward translation of one vertebral body over the one beneath. This pathoanatomical displacement of a vertebral segment distinguishes this process from

spondylolysis, which refers to a defect in the pars interarticularis without displacement of the vertebral body. When referring to spondylolisthesis, the severity of the defect may be classified as low-grade or high-grade. According to the Meyerding classification, HGS is defined as vertebral translation with greater than 50% displacement. In particular, this is based off of the percentage of displacement of the inferior aspect of the body of L5 in relation to the superior border of the sacrum and is graded as follows: no displacement is grade 0; 0% to 25% displacement is grade I; 26% to 50% is grade II; 51% to 75% is grade III; 76% to 100% is grade IV; and more than 100% is grade V (spondyloptosis). In terms of etiology, the Wiltse-Newman classification system is widely accepted when describing the origin of spondylolisthesis in patients. They define 6 etiologies: type I (dysplastic), type II (isthmic), type III (degenerative), type IV (traumatic), type V (pathologic), and type VI (iatrogenic). Type I HGS refers to HGS that is secondary to congenital anomalies. More specifically, this may be secondary to misoriented or hypoplastic facets, sacral deficits, or a poorly developed pars interarticularis, which allow for elongation or eventual separation and forward slippage of the lumbosacral joint with

repetitive loading over time. Type II HGS refers to HGS secondary to defects in the pars interarticularis. Type II HGS is further subclassified into type IIA, type IIB, and type IIC. Type IIA is the most common type, resulting from fatigue failure of the pars interarticularis from repetitive loading and resulting in a complete radiolucent defect. Type IIB is the result of an elongated pars interarticularis secondary to repeated microfractures that heal and can be difficult to distinguish from type I on plain radiographs. Type IIC is the result of a pars interarticularis fracture from an acute injury, elongation of the pars, or a fatigue fracture of the pars. Type III is secondary to degeneration of the disc and facets, which may create instability and mobility on segment. Type IV is secondary to an acute fracture (at a location other than the pars, like type IIC), usually involving the pedicles, facets, or blades. Type V is secondary to pathologic disruptions such as neoplastic and metabolic processes. Type VI is iatrogenic in which disruptions to the musculature, ligaments, facet capsules (removal of .50% of facet joints), removal of 0.5 mm of the pars interarticularis, or disruption of the disc result in subsequent destabilization and slippage

Figure 1: showing meyerding grade of classification for spondylolisthesis

Indications for surgical management of HGS include persistent symptoms, failure of conservative management, radiographic parameters suggestive of imminent slip progression, significant biomechanical stress, and global sagittal imbalance. This section provides an overview of various surgical techniques used in the treatment of HGS in adults, in particular for progression of isthmic slips, which usually present symptomatically when unbalanced. The most common surgical techniques include (1) in situ fusion techniques using posterolateral, anterior, or

circumferential approaches; (2) fusion and reduction combination techniques and (3) vertebrectomy

Aims and Objectives: To study the functional outcome in high grade spondylolisthesis of lumbo & sacral vertebrae patients post-surgery.

Materials and Methods

All patients in whom undergoing posterior instrumentation of lumbar & sacral spine surgery done at raichur institute of medical sciences during the

course of study from september 2022 to september 2023 total data of 30 patients were included in the study

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients with age group >35 yrs of either sex
2. Patients who give informed consent to participate in the study

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patient having other co morbidity and clinical illness
2. Patients having multiple level spine pathology

Results

30 patients with high-grade spondylolisthesis at L5-S1 were operated using this progressive reduction

technique, representing 14 patients grade III (46%), 15 patients grade IV (50%) and one patient grade I (4%).

All procedure was performed in a single operation using a posterior approach. All patients were upright on the second postoperative day. The median follow-up was 12 months. Six months after surgery, 6 patients were pain free and able to stay home without disability.

Only one patient presented persistent L5 sciatalgia. Even if, there was one patient with persistent pain, all of them maintained or improved their daily activities. All patients had good outcomes and returned to their full normal activities within 6 months after surgery. None patient developed deep or superficial infection.

Table 1: Grading of spondylolisthesis Patients

Grading	Number of Patients (n=30)	Percentage %
Grade I	1	4 %
Grade III	14	46%
Grade IV	15	50 %

Table 2: Number of patients turned on after six months follow-up.

Parameter	Number of patients
Pain free	6
With pain	1

Figure 1: Pre op x ray of patient showing L5 over S1 Grade 3 spondylolisthesis

Figure 2: Post op x ray of same patient managed with PLIF

Figure 3: Grading of Patients (N=30)

Discussion

Smith and Bohlman [17] et.al used a single-stage decompression with in situ posterolateral and anterior column fusion to treat high-grade spondylolisthesis. The approach was an isolated posterior approach with anterior column support obtained by using a rib or fibular strut graft placed across the intervertebral disc through the lumbosacral junction. In their series of 11 patients, no neurologic complications or pseudoarthrosis occurred. Their results, followed over an average of 64 months, did not appear to deteriorate with time. Roca et al. [18] in his 14 patients, treated in a similar way, arthrodesis was seen in 12 patients. The two had failure of fusion, due to graft issues – one had fibular strut graft fracture and the other had resorption of fibular graft. Bradford et al. [19]

evaluated 22 patients with high grade spondylolisthesis, treated by reduction and three column supports via a staged anteroposterior procedure, including a first-stage decompression and halo-skeletal traction for reduction, followed by a second-stage anterior arthrodesis. They reported 44% improvement in the slip angle with no significant change in the percentage slip.

They concluded that it was more important to reduce the slip angle to obtain a good result and not necessarily reduction of the percentage slip. Molinarini et al. [20] evaluated 32 patients with high grade spondylolisthesis treated by three techniques: in situ posterior fusion without instrumentation (Group1); reduction, decompression, and posterior instrumented fusion (Group 2); and reduction, decompression with circumferential fusion by an

anterior or posterior lumbar interbody technique (Group 3). Their rate of pseudoarthrosis was 45% in Group 1, 29% in Group 2, and 0% in Group 3. Six reoperations were indicated in the seven pseudoarthrosis, and five were performed. This includes circumferential fusion. In this series four neurologic injuries also occurred. All four patients had slip reduction and fusion. There were four transient foot drops (15%), which took up to a year to resolve. One of the four continued to have a permanent toe extensor weakness at the final follow-up. Boachei [21] et al. in their study of 6 patients obtained fusion in all the 6 patients with a mean follow-up of 42 months.

In high-grade spondylolisthesis, they proclaim, posterior approach is safe and effective in obtaining a solid arthrodesis, restoring sagittal balance, and improving function. They reinforce, that it is the partial reduction of the slip angle, not the percentage slip, in high-grade spondylolisthesis that is important in obtaining optimal results. Dormans [22] et al. in his paper of twenty year experience of treating high grade spondylolisthesis, has divided patients into three groups, viz insitu arthrodesis [A], partial reduction, posterior instrumentation, fusion [B], and reduction, sacroplasty, posterior instrumentation, fusion, wide nerve root decompression, with anterior column support [C]. He proclaims the third [C] group gives the best results with 92% fusion, lesser complications, with greater correction of slip angle, slip percentage, and sagittal pelvic balance. Rajasekharan [23] et.al in his paper of reduction vs in situ fusion in patients with high grade spondylolisthesis, suggests the superior end plate of L5 is to be considered for assessing pelvic parameters after fusion and superior endplate of S1 is to be considered preoperatively in assessing the same parameters.

Three parameters changed significantly postoperatively in both procedures and showed comparable changes – PT, SFD and LSK. Pelvic incidence, sacral slope, lumbar lordosis does not show significant change. This suggests that the improved clinical outcomes for both treatment strategies may co-relate to changes in PT, SFD and LSK and the author call for re-evaluating the need for risky reduction procedures to establish normal pelvic parameters. Kan-min [24] et al. concludes that sacral dome resection from posterior approach in high-grade spondylolisthesis is a shortening osteotomy of the lumbosacral junction. It is very useful for single-stage posterior reduction of L5–S1 with the use of pedicle screws avoiding lengthening of lumbosacral junction and avoiding additional anterior surgery.

This procedure followed by the instrumented fusion of L4–S1 produces a good multidimensional deformity correction with a minimal risk of neurological injury and a satisfactory clinical

outcome. This is a safe surgical procedure to restore spino-pelvic alignment and the sagittal profile of the spine in the treatment of high-grade high dysplastic spondylolisthesis. In their study, L5 incidence improved from 74 to 56 degrees, the lumbosacral angle improved from 15 kyphosis to 6-degree lordosis, lumbar lordosis decreased from 69 to 53 degrees from preoperative to the last follow-up. While pelvic incidence of 77 degree remained unchanged, sacral slope decreased from 51 to 46 degrees and pelvic tilt increased from 25 to 30degrees. Clinical outcome was subjectively rated to be much better than before surgery by 14 out of 15 patients. Four out of 15 patients had temporary sensory impairment of the L5 nerve root which resolved completely within 12 weeks.

There were no permanent neurological complications or no pseudoarthrosis. In our study, slip angle changed from 37.7 to 5.7 degrees, L5 incidence improved from 64.81 to 45.22 degrees, lumbar lordosis decreased from 72.92 to 54.81 degrees from preoperative to the last follow-up. While pelvic incidence of 59.03 degree changed to 50.85, sacral slope decreased from 37.14 to 31.88 degrees and pelvic tilt decreased from 18.14 to 17.33degrees. All the change in parameters were statistically significant, except the change in pelvic tilt

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